

Genetics

Inheritance of thermo-sensitivity for seedling color in japonica variety Fan5

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We isolated a mutant that is thermo-sensitive for seedling color in japonica variety Fan5. Expression of seedling color of Fan5 and four other japonicas was studied at temperatures of 20, 23.1, 26.1, 28, and 30.1 °C in a growth chamber. Seedling color was examined after 10 d. Thermosensitive Fan5 showed variation in seedling color at different temperatures: white at 20 °C, yellow-white at 23.1 °C, yellow-green at 26.1 °C, and green at 28 and 30.1 °C. The other four japonicas were thermoinsensitive for seedling color at all five temperatures.

Crosses of Fan5 and japonica varieties and cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) japonica line 7627 A were grown in 1991 in Hangzhou. In Oct 1992, P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, and BC₁ populations were sown in plastic pots at 20 °C.

Breeding methods

Restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines in rice

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Hybrid rice can only be developed if effective fertility restorers for CMS lines are identified and maintainers are isolated to develop new CMS lines. We evaluated F₁s of 51 hybrids, their 17 pollen parents, and 3 isogenic maintainers (B lines) of CMS lines for spikelet fertility. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications during 1991 wet

Seedling color of thermosensitive Fan5, four thermoinsensitive japonica rice varieties, and their F₁, BC₁, and F₂ populations grown at 20 °C. Hangzhou, China.

Material	Seedling color		χ^2	P
	Green	White		
<i>Parent</i>				
Fan5	0	29		
7001S	37	0		
N5047S	41	0		
Zhenong 1S	16	0		
7627 A	23	0		
<i>F₁</i>				
7001S/Fan5	15	0		
N5047S/Fan5	17	0		
Zhenong 1S/Fan5	21	0		
7627 A/Fan5 ^a	9	0		
<i>BC₁</i>				
7001S/Fan5//Fan5	52	47	χ^2 (1:1)	
N5047S/Fan5//Fan5	38	29	0.162	0.50-0.75
Zhenong 1S/Fan5//Fan5	50	56	0.955	0.25-0.50
7627 A/Fan5//Fan5	44	39	0.223	0.50-0.75
<i>F₂</i>				
7001S/Fan5	153	47	χ^2 (3:1)	
N5047S/Fan5	113	31	0.167	0.50-0.75
Zhenong 1S/Fan5	143	45	0.750	0.25-0.50
			0.638	0.75-0.90

^aF₂ from 7627 A/Fan5 was not tested due to poor seed setting in F₁.

F₁ seedlings from all crosses were green, indicating that thermosensitivity for seedling color in Fan5 is recessive (see table). The segregation ratio of green to white in BC₁ was 1:1 and in F₂, 3:1. Results showed a recessive nuclear gene controls thermosensitivity for seedling

color in Fan5. If the character can be transferred to CMS lines and their maintainers, it could be used as a morphological marker for purifying them by roguing green seedlings at lower temperature. ■

season at RRS. Each 1.7- × 0.2-m plot had a single row of 11 plants at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha and other recommended cultural practices were followed.

Spikelet fertility was assessed on five randomly selected plants in each replication for each genotype. Pollen parents were classified as effective restorers if spikelet fertility was more than 80%, as weak or partial restorers if 20-80%, as weak maintainers if 5-20%, and as effective maintainers if 0-5%.

Fourteen hybrids had more than 80% spikelet fertility, involving nine pollen parents. These pollen parents were identified as effective restorers for CMS lines V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A (see table). These prospective restorers

Maintainer and restorer lines identified for 3 CMS lines at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991 WS.

Pollen parent	Spikelet fertility ^a of hybrid with particular CMS line		
	V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
ADT36	PR	PR	R
ASD16	PR	PR	PR
ASD17	PR	PR	PR
ASD18	PR	R	R
CO 37	PR	R	PR
IR36	PR	PR	PR
IR50	PR	R	PR
IR60	PR	PR	PR
IR64	R	PR	R
IET1444	PR	PR	PR
TKM6	PR	R	R
TKM9	PR	PR	PR
TM4309	PR	R	R
TNAU801793	PR	PR	PR
TNAU88013	R	R	PR
ADT39	M	PR	PR
Jaya	PR	R	PR

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, M = maintainer.

can be purified genetically and then used in developing hybrids.

V20 A/ADT39 recorded 4.3% spikelet fertility, so pollen parent ADT39 was identified as a potential maintainer for CMS line V20 A. This prospective maintainer line will be used in a backcrossing program to develop new CMS lines.

CMS lines V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A, which all have the same wild abortive cytoplasm but different nuclear genotypes, differed in maintainer and restorer frequencies. Genetic background of CMS lines seems to influence their maintaining and restoring abilities.

Restoration-maintenance behavior sometimes differed among pollen parents for CMS lines with the same cytoplasmic source, possibly because of nuclear and cytoplasmic interactions between pollen parents and CMS lines or the heterozygosity of pollen parents. ■

Identifying restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR62829 A and IR58025 A in Myanmar

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CMS lines IR62829 A and IR58025 A were crossed with seven high-yielding rice varieties in 1991 wet season at Hmawbi Research Station and CARI at Yezin. F₁s and their parents were grown in 3-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 1992 dry season. Florets from each plant were collected before flowering and stained with KI solution to determine pollen sterility. Pollen sterility percentage was estimated by counting filled and unfilled grains from harvested F₁ panicles.

Varieties were classified as effective maintainers of male parents if pollen fertility of the hybrid was less than 5%. Male parents were identified as restorers if pollen fertility of the hybrid was more than 80%. Partial maintainers were those with 6-30% pollen fertility

in the hybrid and partial restorers were those with 31-79% pollen fertility.

Varieties Sinekeri 3, BG120 3, Hmawbi 2, and Kyawzeya were found to be effective maintainers for both CMS lines and Sintheingyi, Theedatyin, and

IR50, effective restorers. We will use effective maintainer lines as male parents for backcrossing to develop new CMS lines. Effective restorer lines will be used in hybrid seed production next season. ■

Identifying restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Vietnam

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We identified restorers and maintainers for promising CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Cuu Long Delta of Vietnam. Improved lines and varieties adapted to Cuu Long Delta were crossed with IR58025 A or IR62829 A. F₁ hybrids were grown in the field during 1992 wet season and 1993 dry season. Hybrids and their male parents were transplanted in rows of 30 plants spaced at 20 × 20 cm.

To observe pollen sterility, florets from the upper part of the panicles were collected before flowering and pollen grains were stained with KI. Spikelet sterility was recorded on bagged panicles. When a hybrid showed 99-100% pollen sterility, its male parent was designated as a maintainer for the corresponding female parent (CMS line). When a hybrid showed more than 90% pollen and spikelet fertility, its male parent was identified as a restorer. Other male parents were considered to be partial restorers (see table). The frequency of maintainers for IR58025 A was higher than that for IR62829 A.

Most of the maintainers and restorers identified were adapted to Cuu Long Delta and are being used in a backcross program or to develop new F₁ hybrids. ■

Maintainer and restorer lines identified for CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam, 1992 WS and 1993 DS.

IR58025 A			IR62829 A		
Maintainer	Restorer	Partial restorer	Maintainer	Restorer	Partial restorer
OM43-26	OM53-71	IR72	IR44595-70	OM1037	OM987-1
OM59-7	OM80	OM547	OMCS6	IR42068	OMCS9
OM576	OM725	IR31917		IR35546	OM90-2
MTL 58	OM269	IR43158		IR35311	OM43-26
MTL 61	IR52287-15	IR42068			IR49517
IR44595-70	IR9729	OM987-1			IR64
IR50404	IR64	16B			OM547
IR52280	IR42068				
IR19725	S818B				

Identifying and evaluating photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines in China

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Both photoperiod and temperature regulate fertility alteration of PGMS rice, including the original line Nongken 58 S.

Photoperiod sensitivity in fertility alteration of PGMS occurs only within a specific temperature range. The higher point (HP) of the range affects multiplication of the sterile line. The lower point (LP) affects sterility fluctuation of the PGMS line when occasionally exposed to low temperature under long-day conditions.

We studied the percentages of fertile pollen and spikelet fertility of PGMS lines in China under different temperature